

Is Acute Urine Retention an A typical Presentation of Acute Appendicitis?

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ABSTRACT

The occurrence of acute urinary retention (AUR) in females is relatively infrequent, yet it is noteworthy when observed as a manifestation of acute appendicitis in an otherwise healthy middle-aged woman. Presented herein is the case of a 58-year-old woman who experienced an inability to void urine for 10 hours, accompanied by mild pain initially noted in the suprapubic region and subsequently shifting to the right iliac fossa. Upon admission, the patient exhibited afebrile status and hemodynamic stability. Physical examination revealed a mild tenderness in the lower abdominal region, alongside a palpable bladder situated midway between the symphysis pubis and umbilicus. Bowel sounds were found to be within normal. Laboratory investigations indicated elevated inflammatory markers, and urinalysis disclosed the presence of moderate amount of pus cells. Ultrasonography revealed acute appendicitis with a fecolith obstructing the base of the appendix. This case underscores the challenge faced by surgeons in recognizing the atypical presentation of acute appendicitis and underscores the importance of thorough and repeated abdominal examinations to achieve diagnostic precision.

Keywords: Appendicitis; Acute urinary retention; Unusual presentation.

INTRODUCTION

While the classical presentation of acute appendicitis is widely recognized, characterized by periumbilical pain with subsequent migration to the right iliac fossa accompanied by symptoms such as nausea, vomiting, and anorexia, it is imperative to acknowledge that this constellation of symptoms may not always be present to suggest the diagnosis. There exists limited literature on the atypical presentations of acute appendicitis, necessitating consideration of alternative diagnoses, particularly in cases where acute urinary retention (AUR) manifests. Acute urinary retention, although commonly encountered in the elderly demographic, assumes a notable significance when observed in a healthy adult female individual as a potential manifestation of acute appendicitis.

CASE REPORT

A previously healthy 58-year-old woman presented to the surgical casualty department with a complaint of being unable to urinate for the past 10 hours, accompanied by mild lower abdominal pain. The pain was dull, non-radiating, and not exacerbated or relieved by any specific factors. She denied experiencing nausea, vomiting, fever, or changes in appetite. There was no history of prior urological issues, kidney stones, urethral discharge, or significant medical or surgical events. The patient reported normal bowel habits.

Upon admission, her vital signs were stable, with a normal heart rate, blood pressure, respiratory rate, and oxygen saturation. Physical examination revealed dry mucosa and skin, with tenderness noted in the lower abdomen. Palpation revealed a palpable bladder midway between the pubic symphysis and umbilicus. Bowel sounds were normal, and there were no signs of rebound tenderness. General systemic examination yielded unremarkable findings including per vaginal and per rectal assessments.

A 14-gauge Foley catheter was inserted without complications and draining 450 mL of urine.

Urinalysis revealed a moderate presence of pus cells, and laboratory tests showed an elevated white blood cell count with predominant neutrophils and an elevated C-reactive protein level. A few hours post-catheterization, the patient continued to experience lower abdominal pain, more pronounced in the right lower quadrant. Clinical signs such as Rovsing sign, obturator sign, and psoas sign were negative, while rebound tenderness was positive. An Alvarado score of 6 points was calculated, (2 for right iliac fossa tenderness, 1 for rebound tenderness, 2 for elevated leukocyte count and 1 for leukocyte left shift) reflecting the presence of certain clinical indicators suggestive of appendicitis.

X-ray of the patient

Ultrasound picture of the patient

Following the ultrasound scan assessment, the patient was found to have a dilated appendix measuring 10.5 mm, with multiple high-density foci within its lumen, indicative of appendicoliths. Additionally, mild free fluid and peri-appendiceal inflammatory changes were observed. Based on these findings, the decision was made to proceed with an open appendicectomy. Intraoperatively, a ruptured pelvic appendix with mild local peritonitis was identified. The postoperative course was uneventful, and histological examination confirmed the presence of a suppurative perforated appendix.

DISCUSSION

The diagnostic challenge of appendicitis is well recognized, particularly due to its propensity for presenting with vague and atypical symptoms, which can mimic various other medical conditions. This challenge is further compounded in both pediatric and adult female populations, often leading to diagnostic delays and increased morbidity and mortality rates associated with the condition^[1,2]. Additionally, acute appendicitis exhibits a complex and varied range of presentations, posing difficulties in its recognition, even for experienced clinicians^[3].

Surgeons are frequently confronted with the task of identifying the less common presentations of acute appendicitis and must remain vigilant to avoid misdiagnosis. While it is not uncommon to proceed with surgery for suspected appendicitis in cases where ureteric stones are present, the reverse scenario, wherein urological manifestations mimic acute appendicitis, can also occur. Instances have been reported where conditions such as right-sided pyelitis or ureteric stones have led to surgical intervention with a pre-operative diagnosis of appendicitis^[11].

Although such errors are less common, it is evident that the presence of genito-urinary symptoms in cases of suspected appendicitis can complicate diagnosis. While the majority of appendicitis cases present with clear diagnostic indicators and genito-urinary symptoms are typically secondary, the emergence of such symptoms can introduce diagnostic challenges, even with careful examination.

Appendicitis presenting as acute urinary retention (AUR) is a rare occurrence, particularly among females, owing to the anatomical characteristics of the female urethra. However, urological manifestations of acute appendicitis, such as dysuria, urinary frequency, AUR, and rectal pain, may lead to initial suspicion of genito-urinary pathology^[4].

Literature has documented rare presentations of acute appendicitis, including cases featuring gross hematuria and acute pyelonephritis^[5,6]. Such uncommon manifestations warrant consideration in the differential diagnosis of acute urinary retention (AUR). Review of available literature underscores the infrequency of urinary retention as an initial symptom of acute appendicitis in pediatric patients, with only limited case reports documenting such occurrences^[7,8]. However, incidence rates tend to rise with advancing age, with higher prevalence observed in individuals aged 60 years and older^[8,9].

Notably, Simson et al. emphasize the importance of recognizing AUR as a rare and atypical presentation of acute appendicitis, particularly among otherwise healthy young males^[10]. Urinary retention in this context is attributed to irritation of the bladder sphincter, an uncommon occurrence where difficulty in urination is the prevailing complaint. Furthermore, the likelihood of AUR increases notably in cases of pelvic appendicitis^[11].

While bladder outlet obstruction (BOO) is relatively common among older male patients, the etiology of urinary retention in women encompasses a broader spectrum of conditions, complicating epidemiological research and understanding of underlying pathophysiology^[14]. Available data on the incidence of AUR in women are limited, although a Scandinavian study reported an incidence rate of 7 per 100,000 population per year, with a significant male predominance^[12,13]. However, Female urinary retention is widely recognized as being significantly underestimated and often goes undiagnosed^[15].

CONCLUSION

Given the diagnostic complexity of patients presenting with acute unexplained urinary retention, particularly in the context of concurrent fever, and leukocytosis, healthcare providers are urged to maintain a broad differential diagnosis and exercise a high index of suspicion. When common causes of acute urinary retention are excluded, particularly in female populations unusual or less likely causes need to be explored thoroughly. Early intervention is crucial to prevent disease complications, extended hospital course and health care costs

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